

THE IMPORTANCE OF THE TUTSAN OR SWEET-AMBER WHICH BELONGING TO THE HYPERICACCEAE FAMILY

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Abstract. Presidential Decree of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PD-4670 of the dated April 10, 2020 "On measures to protect medicinal plants growing in the wild, cultured cultivation, processing and rational use of available resources" and No. PD-4901 dated November 26, 2020 "Cultivation of medicinal plants and processing, on measures to expand the scope of scientific research on the development of their seed production" were adopted. According to the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PD-4901 dated November 26, 2020, to study the areas of medicinal plants growing wild in the territory of the republic and identify their reserves, to preserve the gene pool of existing bioresources, to establish mother plantations; A wide range of scientific and practical researches related to cultivation and preparation of seed materials, breeding, establishment of collective nurseries and processing of their raw materials were carried out.

Keywords: digoxin, theophylline, indinavir, cyclosporine anticoagulant, gingivitis, stomatitis, Alzheimer's

Introduction. Tutsan or sweet-amber (Hypericaceae) It is used to collect and dry the grass of field grass, a wild growing perennial herbaceous plant belonging to the family. Tutsan or sweet-amber species are found in all regions of Uzbekistan. These plants grow on roadsides, ditches, meadows, meadows, gardens, bushes, from the slopes of the mountains to the middle part, in small stone-soil areas.

Tutsan or sweet-amber species is a perennial herb, 30-35, sometimes 100 cm tall. The stem is one or more, erect, smooth, hairless, two-edged, the upper part is branched. The leaf is wide or oblong-ovate, flat-edged, and opposite on the stem. The flowers are golden, clustered in a shield-shaped raceme or peduncle. The fruit is a three-digit capsule. It blooms in June and August, the fruit ripens in July and September. During the flowering period, field species are cut 15-20 cm long from the tip of the upper part of the ground, and the shade is dried on the ground. Then it is burned and taken out of the galvir. Large stems are discarded.

Tutsan or sweet-amber species contain flavonoids, essential oil, vitamins, resins, sugars, dyes, and flavoring agents. Abu Ali ibn Sina used the field plant as a pain reliever, diuretic and to treat various wounds. In folk medicine, tincture made from field species is used in the treatment of kidney, bladder, and gastrointestinal (diarrhea) diseases. In addition to these, the tincture prepared from the plant is used as a hemostatic drug (for bleeding from internal organs or spitting up blood). A fresh leaf is chopped, crushed and applied to the wound.

To prepare a tincture from the field species, pour a glass of boiling water into a container with a closed mouth, add 10 grams of the ground upper part of the plant and infuse it. Then it is washed in gauze. The infusion is drunk 2-4 times a day after meals in a tablespoon. In scientific medicine, medicinal preparations of the field plant (tincture, nastoyka, liquid extract) are used in the treatment of gastrointestinal diseases (colitis, diarrhea, oral cavity (gingivitis, stomatitis) and burns of II and III degree. Tincture prepared from the above-ground part of the plant are used in urine and It is recommended to use as an anthelmintic drug.

Decoctions made from the above-mentioned diseases are also used in folk medicine for the treatment of the above-mentioned diseases. In folk medicine, patients with urinary incontinence

are advised to drink the tincture of dalchoi. To do this, put 10 g of the ground part of the plant in a glass of boiling water and leave it for a while. Strain and drink one tablespoon 2-4 times a day. Fenugreek decoction can also be used in the treatment of gastrointestinal diseases.

Pour 1 cup of boiling water on 1 tablespoon of crushed plant and boil for 15 minutes on low heat. After straining, drink a quarter glass three times a day. Fenugreek oil is also useful. To prepare the oil, 1 part of dalchoi is added to 2 parts of olive (almond or peach) oil and left to stand for 3 weeks. It can be used as a compress to treat burns or wounds (for example, trophic ulcers). To treat alcoholism, put 2 tablespoons of dried field tea in 250 ml of boiled water and put it in a water bath for 20-30 minutes. Strain and drink 2 tablespoons before breakfast and lunch.

To prepare the tincture, put 20 g of the herb in an enameled container, pour 200 ml (1 glass) of boiled water at room temperature, cover with a lid and heat in a boiling water bath for 15 minutes and cool at room temperature for 45 minutes. The infusion is filtered through cheesecloth and the remaining raw materials are squeezed. The volume of the obtained tincture is brought up to 200 ml with boiled water. The tincture can be stored in a cool place for up to 2 days. Tincture is taken 2 tablespoons 3 times a day 30 minutes before meals. When used in high doses, digoxin, theophylline, indinavir, cyclosporine, oral anticoagulants may have side effects. Tutsan or sweet-amber medicinal plant is yellow, star-shaped and has been used as a medicinal herb for hundreds of years. Fenugreek oil is widely used in skin cleansing. Its decoction can also be used to relieve depression and treat a number of diseases.

Conclusion

It relieves insomnia, helps to restore skin cells, removes acne scars on the face and skin. Fights against microbes and bacteria, ensures the disappearance of various inflammations occurring in the body, normalizes the digestive system, helps in appetite, normalizes thyroid hormones. Tutsan or sweet-amber also acts as a natural pain reliever.

It relieves muscle pain, prevents the proliferation of cancer cells, helps to clear sputum in case of flu and cold, reduces headache and reduces fever.

It is not recommended in the following cases:

1. To pregnant and near-pregnant women;
 2. People suffering from attention deficit disorder, hyperactive, schizophrenic, as well as people with Alzheimer's (memory loss) disease;
 3. For people taking anti-depressants, blood thinners, and asthma medications;
- It is necessary to stop drinking tea two weeks before surgical procedures that lead to anesthesia. Drinking tea without a break and more than the specified period can cause headache, dizziness, weakness, nausea, dry mouth, skin rashes.

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